

A Review on Formulation and Evaluation of Polyherbal Soap for Anti-Acne Activity

¹Swetha. M, ²Muskaan Abutaher, ³Namann, ⁴D. Suman Choudhary, ⁵T. Rama Rao

¹Professor, Department of pharmaceutics, CMR College of Pharmacy, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.

^{2,3,4}Student, CMR College of Pharmacy, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.

⁵Principal, Department of Pharmaceutical Analysis, CMR College of Pharmacy, Hyderabad, Telangana, India.

Abstract- Natural fatty acids react with sodium or potassium ions to produce soap, a common cleaning solution. Water has a cleansing effect because it bonds to the carboxylic group, while the negative ions in the hydrocarbon chain draw oil and grease. Diverse kinds of soaps are available to meet diverse demands. These include synthetic soaps created through chemical processes and natural soaps prepared from just natural materials. There are also Syndet bars, which contain a mixture of synthetic detergents. To guarantee proper use, it is important to recognize these differences. For example, dish soap should be used for dishes rather than for personal hygiene. Furthermore, soap is available in a variety of forms, including laundry soap that is liquid, powder, or gel; toilet soap that is rated according to Total Fatty Matter (TFM); and beauty soaps that are tailored to particular skin types. Medicated soaps include antimicrobial and antifungal qualities that are beneficial for treating a variety of skin issues. Novelty soaps distinctive forms and patterns make bathing more enjoyable. Transparent soaps with a high glycerin content offer mild cleaning. They are frequently glycerin-based. Generally composed of natural ingredients, handmade soaps provide a safer option than commercial goods. Polyherbal soaps combine plants and herbs to offer medicinal advantages, promoting skin health through their restorative qualities. Physical characteristics like as clarity and odor, pH levels, cleaning effectiveness, amount of moisture, and saponification values are among the physical factors that evaluation tests check for quality and efficacy. Clinical metrics such as the number of acne lesions and assessments of sebum production are evaluated in conjunction with antimicrobial and antioxidant activity. Knowing these features of soap makes it easier to choose the best choice for your needs, whether they are therapeutic, skincare, or personal hygiene-related.

Keywords: Polyherbal soap, Propionibacterium acnes (P. acnes), Polyherbal soap, Total Fatty Matter (TFM), Saponification value, Acne lesion.

1. INTRODUCTION

Blackheads, inflammatory lesions, and scaly red skin are common symptoms of acne, a follicular skin disorder that affects about 85% of teenagers and can last into adulthood. Changes in pilosebaceous unit structures, triggered by androgens, are part of its etiology. Antibiotic-resistant forms of bacteria are evolving despite the use of antibiotics in conventional treatments. Ayurvedic-based herbal substitutes are becoming more popular because of their least adverse effects [1]. Using the healing properties of natural herbs, herbal soaps are a valuable skincare product that can help with a wide range of illnesses and skin issues. Drawn from plant parts including leaves, roots, and fruit, their antibacterial and antifungal qualities function as medications with added moisturizing and lingering fragrance. Including herbal soap in your skincare regimen helps you have a more radiant, healthy-looking complexion by treating infections like ringworm and improving the tone, suppleness, and smoothness of your skin [2]. More and more natural components derived from plants are being used in medicinal soap products to improve their essential biological qualities and lessen the negative impacts of synthetic chemicals. Many of the side effects associated with synthetic substances are mitigated when natural alternatives such as saponins, natural antibacterial agents, and phenolic compounds are used in place of synthetic foaming agents, antioxidants, and antibacterial agents. Ingredients including coconut oil, olive oil, turmeric, sandalwood, jasmine, and lemon essence are frequently found in therapeutic soaps. Hygiene with herbal soap becomes essential in reducing the spreading of illness in healthcare settings, providing a better defense against microbial transmission, given the skin's susceptibility to a variety of disorders and infections[3].

2. SKIN

Skin, the largest organ in the body, covers the external surface and consists of three layers: dermis, hypodermis, and epidermis. It serves as the body's first line of defense against pathogens, UV radiation, and physical

damage. Keratinocytes produce protective protein keratin, while collagen and lipocytes make up the dermis and subcutaneous tissue. The thickness of these layers varies depending on location [4].

3. STRUCTURE OF SKIN

The skin is made up of the basement membrane, which holds the dermis to the epidermis, which is mainly made up of keratinocytes. Beneath the dermis, the hypodermis, which is thick with fat, acts as a cushion and an insulator.

Figure 1: Cross section of skin [5].

4. LAYERS OF SKIN

4.1. EPIDERMIS

The keratinocytes that produce keratin create the stratified squamous epithelium that makes up the epidermis, which acts as a barrier to protect the body. It is composed of five layers: stratum corneum, stratum lucidum, stratum granulosum, stratum spinosum, and stratum basale. Keratinocytes, melanocytes, Langerhans cells, and Merkel cells are among the several cell types found in these layers. The dermo-epidermal junction, which is essential for preserving skin integrity and function, maintains the cohesiveness between the dermis and epidermis[6].

4.2. DERMIS

Fibroblasts, mast cells, neurons, and circulatory networks can enter the dermis, an integrated connective tissue system, which guarantees tensile strength, elasticity, sensory input, and protection from injury. Through its contact with the epidermis, it creates predictable depth-dependent organisation of connective tissue components, resulting in structures like dermal-epidermal junctions and epidermal appendages. The dermis, which is mostly made up of collagen and other matrix elements like elastic fibres, is subject to turnover and remodelling in response to different stimuli, which preserves the integrity and functionality of the skin.

4.3. HYPODERMIS

Fat cells, or lipocytes, start to form in the subcutaneous tissue around the end of the fifth month of embryonic development. These cells are separated from one another by massive blood arteries and fibrous septa made of collagen. The thickness of this adipose layer, known as the panniculus, varies depending on the area of the body. It stores energy and functions as an endocrine organ. Here, hormones are converted, such as androstenedione to estrone by aromatase, and leptin, which is produced by lipocytes and controlled by the brain, contributes to the regulation of body weight[5].

5. DISEASES RELATED TO SKIN

Skin illnesses account for 1.79% of all diseases worldwide, impacting a sizable section of the population. One in four Americans suffer from a skin condition, according to the American Academy of Dermatology Association. The duration and severity of these problems varies; they might be as short-lived as athlete's foot or hives or as long-lasting as vitiligo and psoriasis. Although skin cancer is a major threat, it can be effectively treated if detected early. Furthermore, certain illnesses like cellulitis and carbuncles impact the skin's deeper layers and necessitate immediate medical attention. For an appropriate diagnosis and course of therapy, speaking with a dermatologist or other healthcare practitioner is essential[7].

6. ACNE

The sebaceous glands are impacted by acne, a chronic inflammatory skin condition that is mostly brought on by *Propionibacterium acnes* and increased sebum production. Due to causes such as food, lifestyle modifications, and air pollution, its prevalence has increased globally, resulting in enormous psychological and healthcare costs. Although most cases of acne go away by the time a person reaches 30, it can linger far into adulthood and affect 40–50 million

people in the US, most of whom are between the ages of 12 and 24. Treatment entails addressing a number of variables, including inflammation and follicular keratinization, while taking patient priorities and therapeutic obstacles into account. Acne therapy does not have a documented mortality rate, but it can cause psychological distress and scars, so it is important to treat patients holistically [8].

Figure 2: Acne [39].

7. PATHOPHYSIOLOGY OF ACNE

The several causes of acne include inflammation, androgen-mediated sebum production, follicular keratinization, and *P. acnes* bacterium. *P. acnes* can trigger immunological responses yet contributes to skin health under normal settings. The production of sebum by sebaceous glands protects the skin, but keratinization and androgen activity disturbances can cause acne. Evidence suggests that inflammation may be involved in different stages of acne progression, however this is a contentious topic. Tailored therapy regimens are essential, with a focus on a thorough comprehension of lesion appearance and underlying mechanisms for efficient management[9].

8. TYPES OF ACNE

About 17 million Americans suffer from acne, a common skin disorder that can be divided into two categories: inflammatory (papules, pustules, nodules, cysts) and noninflammatory (blackheads, whiteheads). Salicylic acid and other over-the-counter medications are usually effective in treating noninflammatory acne, but topical retinoids or benzoyl peroxide may be necessary for treating inflammatory acne, which is brought on by bacteria obstructing pores. Prescription medicine may be needed for pustules, nodules, and papules in order to shrink the size of the oil glands and stop additional inflammation. The most severe type, cysts, may require surgery to remove by a dermatologist in order to prevent scarring and frequently require treatment with isotretinoin[10].

Figure 3: Types of acne [40].

9. FACTORS CAUSING ACNE

Acne can be caused by excessive oil, dead skin cells, and bacteria growth, with factors like hormones, family history, medications, and age increasing the risk. Other factors include certain foods, stress, pressure, pollution, and excessive skin scrubs.

One or more of the following might be the cause of acne:

- Excessive sebum production
- Dead skin cell accumulation inside the pore.
- Bacterial growth within the pore.

Any of the following conditions might make you more prone to acne:

- Hormones.

- Background in the family.
 - Drugs.
- The following don't cause acne, but they can make it worse.

- Certain foods.
- Tension.
- Pressure from backpacks, tight clothing, and sports helmets.
- A lot of humidity and pollution.
- Plucking or squeezing pimples.
- Rubbing too vigorously on your skin [11].

10. SOAPS

Naturally occurring fatty acids react with sodium or potassium salts to form soap, a well-known cleaning agent. The hydrocarbon chain's negative ions are responsible for drawing oil and grease to the substance and binding water to the carboxylic group, which is why it has a cleansing effect. In addition to fundamental ingredients, other compounds are added for particular uses, including pharmaceutical additives for medicated soaps. When making soap, metallic ingredients like calcium and magnesium are added, which affects the soap's hardness. Since its accidental discovery in history, soap has been essential to society, evolving from traditional medical remedies to a common cleaning tool [12].

11. TYPES OF SOAPS

Skin cleansers come in a variety of shapes and sizes, such as bars, gels, and foams, and they all have different smells and looks[13].

i. Natural soaps/ Herbal soaps: Similar to organic soap, natural soap is made entirely of natural elements with the possible addition of a small number of synthetic additives, such as colors or perfumes. Even while natural soap is not always certified organic, it still doesn't contain harmful synthetic and artificial ingredients that are found in conventional soap. Usually perfumed with essential oils and colored by natural ingredients like spices and herbs, natural soaps follow a recipe that emphasizes the least amount of artificial ingredients [14].

ii. Synthetic soaps: Oil or fat is combined with an alkali (lye or caustic) in a chemical process known as saponification to create synthetic soap. Triglyceride oils and fats are hydrolyzed in this reaction to produce free fatty acids, which combine with the alkali to make base or crude soap. The latter is made up of different soap salts, excess fat or alkali, water, and glycerin, which is released from the triglyceride as a result of the reaction [15].

iii. Syndet bars: The word "syndet," which combines the words "synthetic" and "detergent," refers to the fact that these cleansers are made by mixing two or more detergent components. As their name suggests, syndets are useful surfactants or tension active compounds that work at the surface to reduce surface tension [16].

It is important to understand the different types of soaps are available because it might not be the best idea to use a soap meant for hygiene reasons on surfaces intended for dishwashing. We'll talk about several kinds of soap and what makes them different.

i. Toilet soaps/ Bathing soaps: While toilet soap and bathing soap share some similarities, toilet soap stands out due to its higher fat content. Compared to bath soap, toilet soap is supposed to have more moisturizing and cleaning qualities because of its higher fat content [17].

Toilet soaps are divided into three grades by the Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) according to the amount of Total Fatty Matter (TFM) they contain:

Grade-1: A minimum TFM concentration of 76% is required for soaps in this category.

Grade-2: The soaps in this class must contain at least 70% TFM.

Grade-3: Soaps of this group must contain at least 60% TFM [18].

ii. Laundry soaps: A lack of natural materials such as wood ash and goat fat has led to a growing reliance on synthetic manufacture for laundry soaps, which come in liquid, powder, and gel forms. Nowadays, a large number of goods marketed as soap are actually detergents, mostly made of synthetic surfactants. Due to their ability to draw both water and dirt, these surfactants are essential for effectively cleaning laundry [19].

iii. Beauty soaps/ Bars: Beauty soaps are made with ingredients specifically designed to cater to a range of skin types and are designed to highlight appealing smells. Glycerin or special oil mixes may be used for additional skincare advantages [20].

iv. Dish soaps: Dish soap is a specific kind of soap that is made with a combination of surfactants that foam easily. It is also referred to as dish soap or liquid for washing dishes. Because dish soap effectively breaks the tension between particles, it is especially excellent at cutting down oils and fats on dishes and pots. These surfactants were chosen for their non-irritating qualities. Some types might also include fragrances, colors, or rinse aids as extra ingredients [21].

v. Guest soaps: Guest soaps are bars of soap designed specifically for use by guests staying at a particular place, like someone's house.

vi. Medicated soaps: Medicated soap is highly valued for its potent antimicrobial, antifungal, anti-inflammatory, insecticidal, and antiparasitic properties. It helps to get rid of rashes, itching, flaking, and other dermatological issues as well as redness and irritation [22].

Antibacterial soaps: Antibacterial soaps, which are also known as antimicrobial or antiseptic soaps, include certain ingredients that aren't found in ordinary soaps. These additional components are added to a variety of consumer goods in an effort to reduce or avoid bacterial illnesses [23].

Antifungal soaps: A type of soap called antifungal soap is made to help people get rid of various fungal infections [24].

Medicated soaps for other skin problems: Apart from fungal and bacterial infections, the skin can also get problems like excessive dryness and blocked pores. Another issue is common acne, for which there are several medicated soaps available on the market. To effectively tackle skin disorders, medicated soaps are preferable over conventional ones when it comes to treatment [25].

vii. Novelty soaps: Novelty Soaps are a fun way to cheer up adults or make children grin while taking a bath. These soaps are made with skin-friendly components and are mild for skin. They are available in a variety of shapes, from insects and dinosaurs to seasonal patterns that are usually available [26].

viii. Transparent/ Translucent soaps: Glycerin soap, often known as transparent soap, is a mild cleanser that is distinguished by its unique clarity, which is attained by carefully choosing its ingredients and avoiding the use of opacifiers. Well-known for having a high glycerin concentration, it is preferred by those looking for a gentle but efficient skincare solution that hydrates the skin [27].

ix. Handmade soaps: Compared to commercial soaps, handmade soaps manufactured from natural components are a safer choice for your skin. Natural sources of additives are used to make these soaps [28].

12. POLYHERBAL SOAPS

Blend of natural components derived from a variety of herbs and plants are used to create polyherbal soap, which is rich in essential oils, vitamins, and minerals and provides therapeutic benefits for skin health. Herbal soap is a popular choice because of its well-known healing, revitalizing, and calming qualities—especially for people with dry or sensitive skin. Made up of plant parts such as seeds, rhizomes, and roots, it has antiseptic, antibacterial, anti-aging, and antioxidant properties. Interestingly, artificial flavors, colors, fluorides, and other ingredients that are frequently found in conventional soap formulations are absent from herbal soap [29].

Figure 4: Polyherbal soaps [41].

13. METHODS USED IN SOAP PREPARATION

Making soap involves a variety of techniques and ingredients, each with special qualities and advantages.

i. Melt and Pour Process: By using a pre-made glycerin foundation and doing away with the need for lye, this method makes soap making easier. It's safe, easy to use, and customizable with different colors, scents, and essential oils.

ii. Cold Process Soap: This age-old technique combines water, oils, and fats with sodium hydroxide, or lye. Soap is created by a chemical process known as saponification. Although this method allows for freedom in ingredients and designs, it does necessitate careful lye measurement and handling.

iii. Hot process soap: Hot process soap is made in a manner akin to cold process soap, but with heat added to hasten saponification. Because of the heat-induced texture, this approach produces a rustic appearance and a speedier cure time.

Every soap base has unique qualities to offer:

i. Glycerin Soap Base: Often used in melt-and-pour soaps, this versatile ingredient comes in clear, white, and vegetarian forms. Glycerin soap is kind to skin and helps the skin maintain moisture.

ii. Lard: A classic soap foundation that has conditioning qualities and creates an opulent, creamy lather. That might not be appropriate, though, for anyone looking for vegetarian or vegan options.

iii. Soap Chips: They are frequently used in the production of liquid soap. They simplify the process of making liquid soap compositions by being convenient and easy to use [30].

14. HERBS USED TO TREAT ACNE

14.1. NEEM

Figure 5: Herbal Neem Soap.

Botanical name: *Azadiracta indica*

Family: Meliaceae

Parts of plants used: Leaves, bark.

Color: Green.

Description: Leaves are compound alternate, rachis 15-25cm long, 0.1cm thick, leaflet with oblique, serrate, 7-8.5cm long and 1-1.7cm wide, slightly yellowish – green in color.

Chemical Constituents: Flavonoids, Alkaloids, Azadirone, Nimbin, Nimbidin, Terpinoids, Steroids, Margosicacid, Vanilic acid, Glycosides, Beta sitosterol, Nimbectin, Kaempeerol, Quercusertin are accessible in leaves of Neem [31].

Benefit for skin: Anti-inflammatory, anti-fungal, anti-bacterial.

Marketed products: Margo bathing soap, Hamam soap bar, Himalaya ayurveda clear skin soap, Khadi natural pure neem soap, Medimix bathing soap.

14.2. ALOE VERA

Figure 6: Herbal Aloe Vera Soap.

Botanical name: *Aloe barbadensis*

Family: Liliaceae

Parts of plants used: Leaves.

Color: Pea green.

Description: Shrubby/ arborescent, perennial, cerophytic, succulent.

Chemical Constituents: Mostly water 90-99.5% and other potentially active constituents like Sugars, Lignin, Saponins, Anthraquinones, Salicylic acid, Amino acids.

Benefits for skin: Treats acne, pimples, sun burns, acts as moisturizer [32].

Marketed products: Ayouthveda aloe vera bathing soap, Herbal aloe vera soap, Vaadi herbals breezy aloe vera soap.

14.3. TURMERIC

Figure 7: Herbal Turmeric Soap.

Botanical name: *Curcuma longa*

Family: Zingiberaceae

Parts of plants used: Rhizome.

Color: Yellow.

Description: Perennial herb, short stem with large simple oblong leaves. Rhizomes are oblong and branched.

Chemical Constituents: Curcumin, Turmerone, Beta sesquiphellandrene, Curcumenol.

Benefits for skin: Anti-oxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-bacterial, treats diaper rash, psoriasis, acne[32].

Marketed products: Medimix ayurvedic turmeric and argan oil bathing bar, Himalaya soap neem and turmeric, Organic turmeric soap rustic art, Ayush purifying turmeric soap.

14.4. TULASI (Holy basil)

Figure 8: Herbal Tulasi Soap.

Botanical name: *Ocimum tenuiflorum*

Family: Lamiaceae

Parts of plants used: Leaves.

Color: Green.

Description: Perennial, softly hairy leaves rich in health promoting anti-oxidants and flavonoids.

Chemical Constituents: Eugenol, Germacrene, Terpenes.

Benefits for skin: Fights acne, Reduces pigmentation [31].

Marketed products: Khadi natural neem tulsi handmade soap, Krishna Tulasi soap, Twasa herbal neem tulsi bath soap, Kaaya natural neem and tulsi handmade soap, Mirah belle organic tulsihaldi purifying soap bar.

14.5. AVOCADO

Figure 9: Herbal Avocado Soap.

Botanical name: *Persea gratissima gaertneri*

Family: Lauraceae

Parts of plant used: Fruits.

Color: Dark green to black.

Description: The evergreen tree *Persea* is 12 to 15 metres tall and is primarily found in the Mediterranean and Southern United States.

Chemical constituents: Avocados contain phenolic compounds (including hydroxycinnamic acids, hydroxybenzoic acids, flavonoids, and proanthocyanins), acetogenins, phytosterols, carotenoids, and alkaloids as their main molecular families of bioactive components [33].

Benefits for skin: Anti-ageing, anti-inflammatory, improves skin elasticity, helps prevent skin damage.

Marketed products: Forever avocado face and body soap, Kaipo avocado face and body soap, Kalastyle modern wash avocado soap, Naturemix avocado bath soap.

15. EVALUATION TESTS

i. Physical parameters: A number of features can be used to evaluate the physical qualities of soap. When contrasted with a white background, clarity is defined as the transparency or translucency that denotes the lack of contaminants. Examining the colour of the soap entails determining its hue, which can vary from clear to different tones based on natural or added substances. The process of evaluating soap's odour include identifying its aroma, which can be either aromatic or unscented. By using touch to evaluate texture and consistency, one may determine how soft, firm, or smooth the soap is. Finally, the proportions and configuration of the soap bar are determined by size and shape, which are also physical factors [30].

ii. pH: The pH range of the skin is 5.4 to 5.9. A 10% concentration soap solution was carefully made by dissolving 10 grams of soap in 100 milliliter volumetric flask of distilled water. A pH meter was used to measure the pH; the electrode was submerged in the solution, and the pH was then recorded [34].

iii. Percentage free alkali: 150 milliliters of distilled water were added to a beaker that held 10 grams of dried soap. The solution was heated for thirty to forty minutes on a water bath under reflux conditions in order to dissolve the soap. Following cooling, the solution was moved to a 250 ml conical flask along with washings, and the volume was adjusted using distilled water. Ten milliliters of the soap solution in the titration flask were mixed with two drops of the phenolphthalein indicator during the titration procedure. The solution was titrated up to a colorless condition using 0.1M HCl [35]. The Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) states that high-quality soaps should include no more than 5% alkali, while the ISO specifies that the minimum amount of alkali in soaps should be 2%.

iv. Foam height: In a 100 ml graduated measuring cylinder, around 1.0 grams of herbal soap was dissolved in about 50 ml of distilled water. After roughly ten minutes of shaking the mixture, the foam height was measured. Next, based on five consecutive experiments, the mean was determined [3]. The foam height should be at least of 9cm for a good formulated soap.

v. Foam retention: A 100 ml measuring cylinder was filled with 25 milliliter of a 1% soap solution that had been made. After securing the cylinder with a hand cover, it was forcefully shaken for ten minutes. For four minutes, the volume of foam was measured at one-minute intervals [36]. The foam height should have retention time of 5 min.

vi. Alcohol insoluble matter: 50 milliliters of warm ethanol were added to five grams of the sample, which were then thoroughly shaken in a conical flask until the material completely dissolved. After that, the mixture was passed through pre-weighed filter paper and 20 milliliters of heated ethanol. The filtrate was then dried for an hour at 105°C, and the dried paper's weight was noted [37]. A successful assessment of alcohol insoluble matter at 15–18% suggests that high-quality soft soaps are produced and that non-soap components are not present.

vii. Total Fatty Matter (TFM): In order to analyze the total fatty matter in a soap sample, about 10g of soap must be heated to dissolve it in 150ml of distilled water. After adding 20% sulfuric acid to the resultant soap solution, it is heated until it turns transparent. The surface film of fatty acids is formed and then hardened by heating and adding 7g of beeswax. The cake is taken out and weighed. The following formula can be used to determine the proportion of total fatty matter:

% Total Fatty Matter = $(A - X)/W \times 100$ where,

X= weight of wax

A= weight of wax+ oil

W= weight of soap [34]. Generally, a TFM (Total Fatty Matter) percentage of at least 76% is needed for quality soaps.

viii. Cleansing efficiency by thumb impression test/ cleansing effect: Hands that had been subjected to various conditions were carefully pressed, keeping a suitable distance, on sterile nutrient agar plates. The impressions of two thumbs were placed separately on a single nutritional agar plate: one thumb was cleaned using medicinal soap, and another thumb washed with control soap. After incubating the plates for 24 hours at 37°C, the development of microbes on the plates is noticed [37].

ix. Moisture content/ hydration: By measuring the moisture content of the soap and drying it until a steady weight was reached, the percent of water present in the soap was determined. The initial weight of the soap, known to be the "damp weight of a sample," was dried in a dryer at temperatures between 100 and 115°C. The soap was weighed again after it cooled in order to ascertain the "dried weight for the sample." Next, the amount of water content was computed using the relevant formula [36]. 15% is the highest amount of moisture that soap can have.

x. Saponification value determination: One gram of fat or oil requires the same amount of potassium hydroxide (KOH) for complete saponification as the average molecular weight of the fatty acids it contains. About 2 grams of the soap samples are heated with a 0.5M KOH solution, initially at 55°C and progressively raising it to 100 degrees Celsius, in order to determine the saponification value. After roughly an hour of constant stirring the boiling mixture, 0.5M HCl is added and titrated using the phenolphthalein as an indicator. The point at which the pink color vanishes is highlighted [34].

xi. Antimicrobial test: The disc diffusion method was used in the antibacterial experiment against two strains of bacteria: Gram-positive (*B. subtilis*) as well as Gram-negative (*S. Typhi*). A 100 µl culture of each microbe, which is containing roughly 100–150 CFU/ml, was used to seed nutrient agar plates. 6 mm diameter discs of filter paper saturated in 400 µl of the testing solutions were carefully set on the agar plates after drying and sanitizing. After incubating the extracts for 24 hours at 37 °C, the width of the zone of inhibition was measured in millimeters to assess the extracts' antibacterial activity [37].

xii. Antioxidant activity: Using the reducing power method, which measures antioxidant activity as an increase in the absorbance of the reaction mixture, greater antioxidant activity or reducing power is determined. The process is mixing 1 ml of the test sample diluted with distilled water (2.5 ml) with 2.5 ml of 0.2 Molar phosphate buffer (pH 6.6) and a 1% w/v solution of potassium ferricyanide. The mixture is recovered after 20 minutes at 50 °C, and 2.5 ml of 10% C₂HCl₃O₂ is added. The upper supernatant layer (2.5 ml) is combined with 0.5 ml of 0.1% ferric chloride and 2.5 ml of filtered water after centrifugation for 15 minutes at 250 rpm. After being exposed to UV light at 700 nm, the resultant solution's antioxidant activity is measured and contrasted with a control [37].

xiii. Acne lesion count: For assessment, a rating system with a range of 0 (no acne) to 10 (the worst possible acne) was used. Subcategories with fractions of 0.25 were established, ranging from 0 to 2. Individuals who scored 0.25 to 1.5 were classed as having physiological acne, also known as "minor acne," and those who scored 1.5 or greater were categorized as having clinical acne, often known as "major acne" [38].

16. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the application of polyherbal soap as a treatment for acne offers a potential approach to managing this prevalent skin issue. Polyherbal soap is an acne treatment that combines different herbal extracts that are known to have antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and skin-soothing qualities. Scientists and dermatologists can learn a great deal about the effectiveness, safety, and tolerance of these formulations through rigorous evaluation methods such as clinical studies, skin sensitivity evaluations, and microbiological analysis. Polyherbal soap is an example of the nexus between conventional wisdom and cutting-edge scientific research, as we endeavour to explore the combined benefits of many herbs and their application in skincare. By utilising the therapeutic properties of plants, we open the door to creative and all-encompassing approaches to treating acne, which will ultimately improve the lives of those who suffer from this skin ailment.

REFERENCES:

1. Rasheed A, Avinash Kumar Reddy G, Mohanalakshmi S, Ashok Kumar CK. Formulation and comparative evaluation of poly herbal anti-acne face wash gels. *Pharmaceutical Biology*. 2011 May 25;49(8):771–4.
2. Majumdar A, Thakkar B, Saxena S, Dwivedi P, Tripathi V. Herbal Soap- Trends, Benefits and Preparation: A Review. *Acta Scientifci Nutritional Health*. 2023 Sep 1;7(9):10–5.
3. R. Margret Chandira, Lokeshwaran S, S. Gracy Gladin. Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Soap by using Melt and Pour Method. www.tnsroindia.org.in ©IJONS: Indian Journal of Natural Sciences; 2022 May p. Vol.13 / Issue 72 / ISSN: 0976 – 0997.
4. Yousef H, Alhadj M, Sharma S. *Anatomy, Skin (Integument), Epidermis* [Internet]. PubMed. Treasure Island (FL): StatPearls Publishing; 2020.
5. Kolarsick PAJ, Kolarsick MA, Goodwin C. *Anatomy and Physiology of the Skin*. *Journal of the Dermatology Nurses' Association*. 2011 Jul;3(4):203–13.
6. Lawton S. *Skin 1: the structure and functions of the skin*. *Nurs. Times*. 2019 Dec;115:30-3.
7. Malcolm W. Greaves. *skin disease | Description, Types, & Treatment*. *Encyclopedia Britannica*. 2020.
8. Yang J, Yang H, Xu A, He L. A Review of Advancement on Influencing Factors of Acne: An Emphasis on Environment Characteristics. *Frontiers in Public Health*. 2020 Sep 17;8(450).
9. Masterson KN. Acne basics: pathophysiology, assessment, and standard treatment options. *Journal of the Dermatology Nurses' Association*. 2018 Jan 1;10(1S):S2-10.
10. Batista AS, Ana P. Types of acne and associated therapy: A review. *Amr. Res. J. Pharm.* 2016;2016:1-9.
11. Nancy Garrick DD. *Acne*. *National Institute of Arthritis and Musculoskeletal and Skin Diseases*. National Institute of Arthritis and Musculoskeletal and Skin Diseases; 2016.
12. Saurav B, Gorakh B pooja, Tiwari N, Bharat K. A review on Herbal soap. *JETIR2212444 Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research*. 2022 Dec;9(ISSN-2349-5162):Issue 12.

13. p-themes. 5 Differences Between Natural And Synthetic Soaps. Rough Beauty. 2016.
14. Wang G. Organic vs Natural vs Synthetic Bath Soaps. Free Bunni. 2023.
15. Coiffard L, Couteau C. Soap and syndets: differences and analogies, sources of great confusion. *European Review for Medical & Pharmacological Sciences*. 2020 Nov 1;24(21).
16. Friedman M. Chemistry, formulation, and performance of syndet and combo bars. In *Soap Manufacturing Technology* 2016 Jan 1 (pp. 73-106). AOCs Press.
17. Jena AB, Panda S. Consumer Buying Behaviour Towards Fmcg Products with Reference to Toilet Soap. *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research (AJMR)*. 2018;7(5):90-113.
18. Nayak C. Why is it Important to Know the TFM Value on Your Soap? Cureskin. 2021.
19. Legesse A. Preparation of laundry soap from used cooking oils: Getting value out of waste. *Scientific Research and Essays*. 2020 Jan 31;15(1):1-0.
20. Wijesundera G, Abeysekera R. Factors influencing the demand of beauty soap among female consumers in the greater Colombo region.
21. Palaniappan K, Karin LY, Shridharan M. Effects of Hand Soap, Detergent and Dishwashing Soap on Bacterial Microbiome, Sebum and pH of Skin. In *IRC-SET 2020: Proceedings of the 6th IRC Conference on Science, Engineering and Technology*, July 2020, Singapore 2021 (pp. 175-183). Springer Singapore.
22. Dravnieks A, Krotoszynski BK. Influence of an Antibacterial Soap. *J. Soc. Cosmetic Chemists*. 1968 Aug 19;19:611-26.
23. Yu JJ, Manus MB, Mueller O, Windsor SC, Horvath JE, Nunn CL. Antibacterial soap use impacts skin microbial communities in rural Madagascar. *PloS one*. 2018 Aug 20;13(8):e0199899.
24. Anuroop UP, KB AH, Kallatra AF, Yasmin F. FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF POLYHERBAL ANTIFUNGAL MEDICATED SOAP FOR SKIN DISEASES.
25. Bettley FR. Some effects of soap on the skin. *British Medical Journal*. 1960 Jun 6;1(5187):1675.
26. Willcox M. Soap. In *Poucher's perfumes, cosmetics and soaps 2000* (pp. 453-465). Dordrecht: Springer Netherlands.
27. Ghaim JB, Volz ED. Skin cleansing bars. In *Handbook of cosmetic science and technology* 2001 Jul 13 (pp. 501-514). CRC Press.
28. Chen LN. Communicating health and wellness: The meaning behind names of handmade soaps. *English Today*. 2019 Mar;35(1):14-9.
29. Manoj GS, Varaprada D, Chanu KA, Ritheesh M, Priyanka KB. FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF POLY HERBAL SOAP. *Pharmaceutical Research*. 2023;13(10).
30. Pawar AP, Pawar DN, Dalvi YV. Formulation and Evaluation of Polyherbal Soap. *Research Journal of Topical and Cosmetic Sciences*. 2019;10(1):23-8.
31. Ghanwat A, Wayzod S, Divya V. Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Soap. *ResearchGate*. 2020.
32. Syal S, Pandit V, Ashawat MS. Traditional herbs to treat acne vulgaris. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*. 2020;10(3):195-201.
33. Salazar-López NJ, Domínguez-Avila JA, Yahia EM, Belmonte-Herrera BH, Wall-Medrano A, Montalvo-González E, et al. Avocado fruit and by-products as potential sources of bioactive compounds. *Food Research International*. 2020 Dec;138(ISSN 0963-9969):109774.
34. Anu P, Anar P, Jahanvi P, Hemal B, Patel A. Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Soap *Corresponding Author. *IJSRR*. 2022;2022(2):42-72.
35. SHARMA S, PRADHAN S, PANDIT B, MOHANTY JP. FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL SOAP TAKING DIFFERENT BIOACTIVE PLANTS BY COLD SAPONIFICATION METHOD. *International Journal of Current Pharmaceutical Research*. 2022 Sep 15;Vol 14, Issue 5, 2022(ISSN- 0975-7066):30-5.
36. Kondepudi, Manjusha & P, BALAKRISHNAIAH & R, SYAMALA & N, MOUNIK & T, RAVI. (2019). the FORMULATION AND EVALUATION OF HERBAL BATH SOAP CONTAINING METHANOLIC EXTRACTS OF THREE AYURVEDIC VARNYA HERBS. *Asian Journal of Pharmaceutical and Clinical Research*. 213-215. 10.22159/ajpcr.2019.v12i11.35158.
37. Stillman RC. The analysis of soaps. *Journal of the American Oil Chemists' Society*. 1952 Nov;29(11):573-6.
38. Thappa D, Adityan B, Kumari R. Scoring systems in acne vulgaris. *Indian Journal of Dermatology, Venereology and Leprology*. 2009;75(3):323.
39. Acne News, Articles and Research. *News-Medical*.
40. Zhang P. The 6 Types of Acne: How to Tell If Your Acne Is Mild, Moderate, or Severe. *How Med Works*.
41. #Ayurveda: Five incredible benefits of Ayurvedic soaps. *The Times of India*. 2021 Feb 2;